

D6.5 (M48) - Report on marine biodiversity resources (an ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR₃ deliverable)

Project name: ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR
Project number: [322392](#)
Report prepared by: Terje Klemetsen
Contributors: Lars Grønvold (LG), Terje Klemetsen (TK)
Date: 2025-12-12
DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855158>
Keywords: Marine reference databases, SalmoBase, MarRef, MMP

Context

ELIXIR₃ - strengthening the Norwegian Node of ELIXIR, is operating molecular reference databases for salmon, salmon lice, and prokaryotes from the marine domain. This report, Deliverable 6.5, concerns the activities and operation of these databases in terms of technical and content updates by Work Package 6 (WP6).

The SalmoBase (<https://salmobase.org>), LiceBase (<https://licebase.org>), and the microbial databases held in the Marine Metagenomics Portal (MMP, <https://sfb.mmp2.sigma2.no>, hosting the databases MarRef, MarDB, SalDB, MarFun, and MarVirus) are central to ELIXIR₃ and the ELIXIR Norway Service Delivery Plan. These databases play crucial roles in advancing research within their respective domains, providing annotations encompassing functional assignment and taxonomic classification for the topics circumscribing lice genomics, salmonid genetics, and microbial communities in marine environments. The operation of these resources necessitates maintenance, upgrades, and expansion of reference data to provide up-to-date and available services for researchers in the domains and biodiversity at large.

Delivery

SalmoBase (by LG)

- **Technical updates:**

- Gene expression visualisation on gene page. import from Bgee or local tsv files.
- Improvements to the JBrowse autoconfig to make it easier to add tracks
- Improved support for import of genomes with custom annotations
- Cross-assembly gene-id-mapping
- **New content:**
 - Added comparative gene expression and ATAC-seq dataset (“rewired”) for Atlantic salmon, rainbow trout and coho salmon
 - Added gene expression from Bgee (Atlantic salmon ICSASG_v2 Ensembl only)
 - Aqua-Faang Tracks - ChromHMM, annotated robust peaks, blacklist, alignment bigwig
 - New assembly Arctic charr (fSalAlp1.1)

Marine Metagenomics Portal (by TK)

Ongoing technical deliveries:

- The MAR databases include MarRef, MarDB, and SalDB, currently hosted at <https://sfb.mmp2.sigma2.no>, and is planned to utilize the metadata system MetaTrack (<https://github.com/ELIXIR-NO/metatrack>) which is in development.

Content updates and curation deliveries:

- Initially not available due to outdated technical infrastructure, the first draft version of MarVirus, consisting of 115 marine viruses with a sequenced genome in either draft or complete status, has been published on <https://sfb.mmp2.sigma2.no>.

Outcomes

- The deliverable has advanced the technical and content capabilities of key marine biodiversity resources under ELIXIR3. SalmoBase has been enhanced with new features such as gene expression visualization, cross-assembly gene-ID mapping, and the integration of new datasets, including comparative gene expression and ATAC-seq data for multiple salmonid species. These updates improve the utility of SalmoBase for researchers in salmonid genetics.
- The Marine Metagenomics Portal (MMP) has seen the publication of the first draft of MarVirus, a curated database of 115 marine viruses, alongside ongoing technical improvements to the MAR databases (MarRef, MarDB, and SalDB). These updates ensure that the databases remain accessible, supporting research in marine microbial communities and biodiversity.